

Integrated Networks and Services for Sustainable Rural Digitalization

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Abstract— This paper examines the COMMECT project's initiatives to overcome the digital divide in rural areas through the deployment of integrated terrestrial (cellular XG, public and private 5G networks, Internet of Things, NB-IoT, LoRa, etc.) and Non-Terrestrial (satellites, drones) Networks. The project has established five user-centric Living Labs across Europe, focused on viticulture (Luxembourg), forestry (Norway), livestock transport (Denmark), olive farming (Türkiye), and sustainable agriculture (Serbia). To facilitate connectivity decision-making, the project is developing a Decision-Making Support Tool (DST), which leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) to provide tailored connectivity recommendations. This paper outlines the project's approach, the integrated networks deployed in the Living Labs, and the DST's functionalities and future developments.

Keywords—digital divide, rural connectivity, COMMECT, DST, LLM.

I. INTRODUCTION

In rural areas, the digital divide remains a significant barrier, hindering access to advanced digital technologies and sustainable practices essential for development and innovation. This digital divide, characterized by the disparity in access to information and communication technologies (ICT) between urban and rural areas, limits opportunities for education, healthcare, economic growth, and overall quality of life. In Europe, a 13% gap in digital technology access persists, primarily affecting rural and remote areas due to their lower commercial attractiveness [1]. This lack of connectivity not only affects individual residents but also hinders the economic development and sustainability of these communities. The COMMECT project, funded under the Horizon Europe programme, aims to bridge this divide by establishing five Living Labs (LLs) in some of these rural and remote areas, where connectivity solutions, focused on integrated networks and services, will be tested in real-life settings.

COMMECT's primary objectives include:

1. *Empowerment of Rural and Remote Communities*: By providing easy access to fast and reliable broadband Internet and educating communities on digital technologies.

2. *Increase Competitiveness and Access to Opportunities*: By designing innovative, cost-effective, and energy-efficient connectivity solutions.
3. *Facilitate Decision-Making for Connectivity*: By developing a Decision-making Support Tool (DST) to advise on the best connectivity solutions based on economic, geographic, and technical factors.
4. *Contribute to Climate Change Mitigation and Resilience*: By designing connectivity solutions that enhance energy efficiency and sustainability.

The aim of COMMECT is to connect the “unconnected”, focusing on bringing digital infrastructure and services to areas that have been traditionally overlooked. By leveraging advancements in 5G (Fifth Generation wireless technology) network infrastructures, integrating terrestrial networks with Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) such as satellites and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), COMMECT seeks to provide comprehensive connectivity solutions tailored to the specific needs of rural and remote communities. The project not only assesses the technical feasibility of these solutions but also their socioeconomic and environmental impacts, adhering to Green ICT principles [2].

While numerous connectivity solutions are available, their appropriateness varies widely in rural and remote areas, leaving end-users uncertain about the best solution option to choose. Through the development of the DST, COMMECT enables end-users to make informed decisions about connectivity options, thus enhancing their digitalization and competitiveness. The DST aims to eliminate this uncertainty by offering a ranked list of optimal solutions suited to specific scenario. The DST guides users in selecting the most appropriate solutions based on their specific needs and environmental contexts.

The DST uses Large Language Models (LLMs) as the underlying technology, which has witnessed rapid development over the last two years. Models such as Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) [3], exemplify this progress, and can produce, manipulate, and comprehend text in a human-like manner. These models are currently used in various domains, including coding (GitHub Copilot)

[4], language translation (DeepL) [5], and agriculture (AgriBERT) [6], though commercial off-the-shelf tools for domains like agriculture and transport are not yet widely available. Recent research on the digitalization of agricultural extension services highlights the potential of AI and large language models, but also emphasizes challenges such as weak institutional capacity and inadequate access to high-quality data and scientific knowledge, which limit their effective deployment [7]. LLMs show potential as human-machine interfaces to facilitate agricultural extension services by simplifying scientific knowledge and providing personalized recommendations [8]. Unlike traditional decision support systems used in agriculture [9], which often rely on predefined models and datasets, the DST utilizes LLMs to provide more dynamic and context-aware recommendations.

This paper introduces the COMMECT project focusing on the DST and its usage in the Living Labs and the connectivity platforms. The paper is organised as follows: Section II elaborates on the COMMECT approach, detailing its concept and methodology. Section III describes the various integrated networks and services identified for the LLs, Section IV details the five LLs and Section V covers the DST, presenting its objectives, functionality and architectural design. Finally, section VII offers conclusions and future directions of this work.

II. COMMECT METHODOLOGY

A. General Methodology

The COMMECT methodology follows a “bottom-up” approach, starting with rural end-users, whose needs and challenges drive the decision-making process. The project began by engaging with all stakeholders to understand their specific needs through surveys, workshops, and consultations. These insights were then mapped into concrete use cases and requirements, which guide the selection of connectivity solutions.

Fig. 1. COMMECT Conceptual Framework.

The COMMECT framework, as shown in Fig. 1, provides a high-level overview of how different elements interact without detailing technical specifics. It illustrates the project’s multi-actor, multi-sector approach, showing how end-users and advisors (experts, policymakers) collaborate to co-create solutions. The business models

integrate socio-economic and environmental factors, ensuring that proposed solutions are both financially viable and scalable, which supports the project's goals of improving sustainability, digitalization, and competitiveness in rural areas.

The connectivity needs of the agriculture and forestry sectors, including data requirements, connectivity objectives, and user interactions are understood and then documented in project deliverables and then used later to train the decision-making components of the DST developed later in project. End-user queries are the input to the DST in the form of natural language prompts.

The DST processes these prompts by leveraging its domain expertise, which includes EU socio-economic and environmental Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), input from end-user advisors, and data on network performance. This structure enables the DST to align COMMECT’s connectivity solutions with the specific needs of rural communities, helping to identify and propose suitable business models and technologies. Connectivity options are further analyzed by the Intelligent Connectivity Platform (ICP), which provides specialized insights and ranks the optimal solutions based on technical and contextual factors.

By integrating the collected data from end-user needs, regional conditions, and expert inputs, the DST helps rural communities navigate their limited technology options, ensuring that both connectivity solutions and business models are tailored to local socio-economic and environmental factors.

B. Connectivity Choices

COMMECT recognizes the necessity of integrating diverse technologies to address the unique challenges faced by rural and remote areas. This includes combining terrestrial networks (such as 5G) with Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) like satellites and UAVs. This hybrid approach ensures reliable, cost-effective, and scalable connectivity solutions that meet the specific needs of different sectors, including agriculture and forestry.

For non-experts in rural communities, selecting the right technology can be overwhelming. The DST simplifies this process by providing refined recommendations based on user inputs and local conditions. The DST offers a user-friendly interface where non-experts can easily input their requirements and receive a ranked list of optimal connectivity solutions. This approach presents technology choices in user-appropriate language, making it accessible and actionable for those end-users.

III. INTEGRATED NETWORKS AND SERVICES

A. Connectivity Platforms

COMMECT’s integrated connectivity platforms combine multiple network types to offer comprehensive coverage and robust performance. These platforms include:

1. *Terrestrial Networks*: Utilizing 5G and other wireless technologies to provide high-speed internet access.
2. *Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs)*: Incorporating satellite and UAV technologies to extend connectivity to remote and hard-to-reach areas.

3. *Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWANs)*: Enabling energy-efficient communication for IoT devices, crucial for applications in smart agriculture and environmental monitoring.

These platforms ensure uninterrupted connectivity and optimal network performance specialized to the specific needs of each use case in the Living Labs.

COMNECT's Living Labs leverage multiple IoT sensor data collection methods across different locations. LoRaWAN is used in the Luxembourg and Serbia labs for vineyard management and sustainable agriculture, respectively. Direct IoT-to-satellite connections are implemented in Luxembourg, and on-the-road applications in Denmark for livestock transport. Additionally, LTE-M, RedCap, and NB-IoT technologies are deployed in the Türkiye lab for olive tree farming.

B. Multi-Sector Services

COMNECT offers specialized network services catering to the distinct requirements of various sectors:

1. **Agriculture**: Implementing precision farming technologies, enabling real-time monitoring of crops, soil, and weather conditions to optimize resource use and increase yield.
2. **Forestry**: Providing connectivity solutions for efficient forest management, including remote monitoring of forest health, automated logging operations, and real-time data collection.
3. **Livestock Transport**: Ensuring animal welfare through connected transport systems that monitor environmental conditions and track livestock movements.
4. **Environmental Preservation**: Supporting conservation efforts with IoT sensors and data analytics to monitor and protect natural resources effectively.

These services are designed to leverage the strengths of integrated connectivity platforms, delivering solutions that enhance productivity, sustainability, and resilience in rural and remote areas.

IV. LIVING LABS IMPLEMENTATION

A. Overview of Living Labs

As depicted in Fig. 2, the COMNECT Living Labs are located throughout Europe and tackle the following use case themes at the location listed:

1. Digitalization of Viticulture in Luxembourg,
2. Connected Forestry in Norway,
3. Connected Livestock Transport in Denmark,
4. Smart Olive Tree Farming in Türkiye, and
5. Sustainable Agriculture in Serbia.

Fig. 2. COMNECT Living Labs.

COMNECT employs a participatory approach in these labs involving end-users, ICT experts, telco and satellite operators, farmers, advisors, and policymakers. Stakeholders include local communities, government agencies, technology providers, and research institutions. Their active participation ensures that the solutions are practical, sustainable, and aligned with user needs. This structured approach facilitates the co-creation of solutions and supports continuous feedback loops, essential for the iterative refinement of technologies in Living Lab environments. Policies that support local community engagement and capacity building are crucial to ensure rural communities can fully leverage these new connectivity solutions. Table I summarizes the KPIs, challenges, and target outcomes for each Living Lab.

TABLE I. OVERVIEW OF LIVING LABS, KPIs, AND CHALLENGES

Living Lab	KPIs	Challenges	Target Outcomes
Luxembourg	Packet Delivery Ratio > 90%, Latency < 400 ms, Uplink 5 Mbps	Terrain, Multi-source data	Better grape quality, lower environmental impact
Norway	Uplink > 10 Mbps, Latency < 100 ms, Reliability 99.9%	Forest terrain, remote coverage	Efficient logging, reduced labour, better monitoring
Denmark	Uplink 16 kbps, Downlink 8-14 Mbps, Reliability 99.9%	Poor rural coverage	Improved animal welfare, real-time monitoring
Türkiye	Access Success 90%, Power -12%	Network coverage	Higher olive yield, reduced pesticide use
Serbia	Max Power 30 kW, Sensor Battery > 2 years	Energy, large area coverage	Optimized water use, real-time monitoring

B. Technological Infrastructure

Despite the capabilities already provided by next-generation wireless networks (XG), there is a growing demand from both industry and society, particularly in rural areas where NTN is crucial, as highlighted by ongoing work in 3GPP on Rel-19 NTN [10]. More advanced technologies are essential for low-cost and accessible network solutions, ultra-dense networks, convergence with cloud and IT, edge computing, and backhauling to remote areas [11].

TABLE II. TECHNOLOGIES AT COMNECT LIVING LABS

Living Lab	Technology
Luxembourg	Satellite Backhauling, IoT-to-NTN access, LoRaWAN, Drone – data collection, Edge Computing
Norway	Network on Wheels, 5G/4G Private networks, Edge Computing
Denmark	5G/4G Private networks, 5G/4G Public network, Wi-Fi, LoRaWAN, TN-NTN connectivity (LEO satellite access, IoT-to-NTN access)
Türkiye	XG (mainly 4G/5G), NB-IoT, eMTC
Serbia	4G commercial, LoRaWAN, Edge Computing

In Table II, the labs and their corresponding technologies are catalogued. A wide range of terrestrial and non-terrestrial technologies are utilized in these LLs and these connectivity solutions are then used as the content for the ICP and DST knowledge bases. The scenarios analysed demonstrate the integration of 5G NTN with terrestrial technologies like Wi-Fi, LPWAN, and LTE, as well as aerial and space-based networks. This integration is essential for providing seamless connectivity and wide

coverage, enabling continuous monitoring and data transmission for activities like weather sensing and agricultural management, thereby enhancing real-time decision-making and operational efficiency in rural settings. While the current infrastructure in the Living Labs does not fully represent complete 5G or future 6G NTN integration [12], the use cases align with 5G-NTN objectives, including seamless connectivity, NTN backhauling for 5G, vehicle tracking, disaster response connectivity, and rural applications. Such integrations are crucial for enhancing quality of life by improving access to essential services such as telemedicine, online education, and digital government services in rural areas. The solutions described previously are integrated and tested within the LLs, with the intention to remain open to evolving connectivity options in the future, such as different work items of NTN (both NTN-New Radio and NTN-IoT) described in Rel-17 and Rel-18. As such, the DST's advisory on connectivity platforms is not confined to those solutions in these five LLs.

C. Luxembourg LL: Digitalisation of Viticulture

The Luxembourg LL is located in the viticulture regions of Luxembourg, focusing on enhancing vineyard productivity and sustainability. Technologies used include satellite backhauling, data collection via LoRaWAN and by UAVs, direct IoT-to-NTN access, and edge computing. This LL addresses challenges such as drought stress, plant health protection (e.g., against leaf diseases). Meteorological sensors and cameras collect data on microclimatic conditions, consistently monitor on plant states, respectively. This data is processed to assist winegrowers in making decisions regarding irrigation, fertilization, and pesticide application. Monitoring microclimate conditions, crops, and plants with connectivity solutions and digital tools is essential to manage viticulture challenges. Outcomes include improved vineyard management, reduced environmental impact, and lower costs for farmers.

D. Norway LL: Connected Forestry

The Norway LL operates in Norway's extensive forest regions, focusing on improving forestry operations and safety. Technologies used include 5G/4G private networks, edge computing, and rural-specific solutions like Network on Wheels. Drones provide real-time data to assist operators in logging, thinning, and forest care. Operators can receive assistance from experts independent of geographic location. Information from cameras and sensors on drones aids in decision-making, and helps protect vulnerable biotopes and species. Additionally, the lab enhances situational awareness for emergency services, aiding fire prevention and response efforts. Potential outcomes from this lab include increased value creation in forestry, improved worker safety, and better protection of biotopes and species.

E. Denmark LL: Digitalisation of Livestock Transport

The Danish Lab focuses on improving the efficiency and welfare of livestock transport across Denmark and other European countries. Technologies used include 5G/4G private and public networks, Wi-Fi, LoRaWAN, TN-NTN connectivity, and direct IoT-to-NTN access. This lab automates tasks such as livestock counting and disease detection, license plate recognition, and route optimization. Ensuring animal fitness for transport and managing choices relevant to animal welfare during loading and transport are

essential, as livestock transport is highly regulated. Connectivity solutions enable continuous monitoring of journey conditions and compliance with regulations. These solutions focus on loading and unloading locations as well as during the transport. Outcomes include optimized transport processes and improved compliance with health standards.

F. Türkiye LL: Smart Olive Tree Farming

The Türkiye Lab is located in olive-growing regions of Türkiye, focusing on the sustainable cultivation of olives, a staple in the region's agriculture. Technologies used include XG (4G/5G), NB-IoT, and Enhanced Machine Type Communication (eMTC) for data collection and monitoring. This lab addresses challenges such as olive fruit fly and ring spot disease through remote sensing and connectivity solutions. These technologies enable early detection and mitigation strategies, optimizing irrigation and pesticide use. Data acquisition, encompassing imagery and metrics collected via sensor arrays deployed within olive groves, is facilitated through various future generation networks and IoT communication protocols. Outcomes include sustainable olive production, reduced environmental impact, and improved economic viability for farmers.

G. Serbia LL: Sustainable Agriculture and Preservation of Natural Environment

The Serbia Lab focuses on sustainable agriculture and environmental preservation in Serbia's rural areas. Technologies include mobile solar generators, LPWAN networks, weather stations, soil sensors, and edge computing. This LL aims to address inefficiencies in traditional agricultural practices, which often lead to increased production costs and significant environmental impact. Key steps include the establishment of LPWAN infrastructure, installation of weather stations and soil sensors, utilization of mobile solar generators, and data integration and analysis. These measures optimize irrigation cycles, reduce pesticide use, and lower environmental impact through data integration and analysis. Outcomes include higher crop yields, cost optimization, better resource management, reduced reliance on pesticides, and enhanced sustainability of farming practices.

H. Business Model Formulation

Business model development for connectivity solutions in rural areas was a key focus for the project. Each LL required tailored business models to address its unique socio-economic context and connectivity needs. Through literature reviews and interactive sessions with LL stakeholders, the project developed a reference framework to guide the design of these models. The business models also feed into the DST's knowledge base, ensuring that the recommendations provided by the tool take into account the socio-economic realities, financing structures, and deployment strategies that are critical for long-term sustainability. The DST leverages these models to provide tailored solutions for users based on their needs and location. For instance, in the Türkiye LL, the local government plays a pivotal role in financing connectivity solutions, such as supporting olive tree farmers to enhance economic performance. Conversely, in the Danish LL, truck companies are inclined to invest in connectivity solutions to optimize business processes, like tracking the condition of

piglets during transportation, thus improving service propositions for their customers.

V. DECISION-MAKING SUPPORT TOOL

A. Overview and Objectives

The DST is central to the COMTECT project's objective of empowering stakeholders like farmers, foresters, and community members in selecting optimal technological solutions. The DST processes user queries and available technologies to generate advice aligned with EU socio-economic and environmental goals [13]. The DST also supports the projects' goal of extending broadband connectivity in rural and remote areas by intelligent use and extension of existing network infrastructure. The integration of NTN with terrestrial cellular networks, and low-cost IoT can enhance the reach of agriculture ICT services.

B. DST and Integrated Network Architecture

The overall COMTECT architecture, as shown in Fig. 3. is structured into four layers, building upon the conceptual framework to detail system interactions and functionalities.

Fig. 3. COMTECT Architecture.

This layered architecture aligns with the principles of telecom management architecture [14], employing a hierarchical structure to decouple and modularize the system components. The layers and their specific role are as follows:

1. User Portal: the application frontend;
2. DST: the application backend;
3. ICP: the service and network manager;
4. Connectivity Platforms: the physical infrastructure of all available networks.

The uppermost layer is the User Portal layer that facilitates direct user engagement through a ChatGPT style interface. The DST is the next layer that processes data and user inputs to support decision-making. The ICP serves as the third layer, managing and optimizing connectivity solutions and augmenting the DSTs knowledge on the available connectivity solutions. Finally, the Connectivity Platform layer underpins the architecture, encompassing a broad range of technologies and infrastructures to deliver comprehensive connectivity solutions. The DST serves as an advanced AI assistant, specifically trained on rural connectivity domains (using Living Labs information), capable of generating context-aware solutions. It relies on a specialized agroforestry knowledge base (AGRI-KB), which provides domain-specific information, and an LLM for data analysis and decision-making support.

C. Architectural Design

The DST relies on the AGRI-KB knowledge base and an LLM to process data and provide connectivity recommendations. These components process diverse data, facilitating the assessment of technologies and their impacts. The tool's architecture includes a feedback loop, enabling continuous improvement based on user input and interaction. Fig. 4 illustrates the key elements of the DST, featuring a chat-based user interface providing users with a straightforward entry point, the processing and embedding of user queries via an LLM, and the execution of semantic searches across various databases to retrieve necessary information, culminating in the creation of natural-language responses in the style of end-user advisors from the agriculture and forestry domain. On the right hand side of Fig. 4 it shows the process where the LLM extracts pertinent

Fig. 4. DST architecture (includes ICP)

information from datasets and documents to populate the structured databases with COMMECT knowledge.

D. Integration with Intelligent Connectivity Platform

The DST's effectiveness is improved by integrating the ICP, which specializes in evaluating connectivity options (see lower part of Fig. 3). This integration enables a focused analysis of available technologies, considering factors like cost, environmental impact, and user-specific needs. The DST, supported by ICP, becomes a useful tool for providing informed connectivity recommendations.

The ICP acts as a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) system for the DST, pulling in specialized connectivity data to improve the DST's recommendations and decision-making [15]. RAG systems boost LLMs by merging their general knowledge with specific data, in this case, connectivity data. This setup enhances the accuracy of DST responses by minimizing errors, or "hallucinations," because it relies on verified information. The ICP and DST work together to provide a more accurate evaluation of connectivity options, ensuring that recommendations are well-suited for agriculture and forestry needs and optimized for connectivity efficiency.

As shown in Fig. 5, the ICP features a Connectivity Facilitator component that integrates a database containing knowledge on connectivity, including solutions and KPIs, termed XG Connectivity KB. It uses LLM embeddings to perform similarity search [16], allowing the system to quickly retrieve relevant information based on user queries and provide tailored connectivity insights. The Connectivity Facilitator integrates with the DST through a ICP Query API using ReST-style communication (Representational State Transfer). The ICP supports the DST by generating a ranked list of optimal connectivity solutions, customized for specific use cases.

Fig. 5 Intelligent Connectivity Platform.

The Intent Management component handles translating user requirements into actionable connectivity instructions for lab facilities. It employs standardized APIs, such as TM Forum APIs, to execute tasks like service ordering [17] and intent-based management [18]. Through this process, the system facilitates the deployment of selected connectivity solutions, ensuring alignment with the user's defined goals and operational needs.

The ICP is designed to receive both the DST user requests and KPIs from the DST, evaluate them, and return

the best available connectivity options. On the connectivity platform side (southbound), the ICP communicates with technology providers, who supply connectivity information either through a catalog or in real-time during runtime. When a user query comes in, the ICP converts the prompts into numerical values using an embedding model. It then searches its databases, including a vector database (which stores data from connectivity providers) and an internal database, analyzing KPIs to determine the most suitable connection.

For example, if a user query specifies a connectivity KPI of 80-100% availability, the ICP might return 4G or 5G network options based on their suitability. Should the query criteria change, such as lowering the KPI threshold, the ICP dynamically adjusts its response, offering different options based on the revised conditions.

This flexible and intelligent process allows the ICP to match connectivity options to the specific needs of a given request, ensuring the best possible outcome based on the data and KPIs provided.

E. Decision process flexibility using LLM

LLM-based decision making offers several advantages over conventional approaches, including greater flexibility, adaptability, and the potential for more optimal decisions. Conventional methods such as decision trees, Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and Logistic Regression (LR) are widely used due to their well-understood properties and effectiveness in decision support systems. However, each of these methods has limitations in flexibility and adaptability compared to LLM-based decision making, as shown in Table III. Decision trees, for instance, are prone to overfitting without proper pruning, limiting their ability to generalize. SVMs require careful selection of kernels and parameters, which may not be optimal for all data patterns. Logistic regression is often inadequate for modeling non-linear relationships and complex feature interactions.

TABLE III. CONVENTIONAL VERSUS LLM-BASED APPROACHES

Feature	Conventional Approaches	LLM-based Decisions
Decision order	Predetermined sequence	Dynamically determined
Flexibility	Inflexible	Flexible
Optimality	Not always optimal	Adapt to specific situations

In contrast, LLMs provide a flexible, dynamic approach to decision-making. They adapt to specific inputs, generating recommendations in real time without needing manual feature engineering. LLMs are particularly well-suited for DST applications due to their ability to process natural language queries, understand the context, and adapt to various decision-making scenarios dynamically.

F. Integration of Large Language Models

LLM's serve as the all-important component in both the DST and ICP, empowering these systems to perform the most complex tasks such as analysing textual data, interpreting natural language queries, and extracting pertinent information. These models are necessary for processing unstructured data sources, including documents, reports, and user interactions, thus populating the AGRI-KB store of the COMMECT knowledge, as shown previously in Fig. 3.

The LLM approach is particularly proficient in contextual understanding, enabling the DST to generate relevant insights and recommendations for the end-users. It analyses patterns, identify correlations, and interprets user input to offer end-users fluent advice backed by COMMECT’s own curated materials and deliverables.

G. Future Developments and Validation

The effectiveness of LLMs in a DST role depends not only on their integration into a DST framework, but primarily on the quality of the data that they are trained on. Ensuring diverse, high-quality, and up-to-date data sets is crucial for maintaining the accuracy and reliability of the DST’s recommendations. All future developments of both the DST and ICP will involve validation in subsequent project phases to ensure effectiveness, with feedback from deployed LLMs informing improvements.

VI. CONCLUSION

The COMMECT project addresses the digital divide in rural and remote areas by integrating advanced digital technologies and connectivity solutions. By leveraging the capabilities of 5G and NTN such as satellites and UAVs, COMMECT implements a holistic approach across five Living Labs in Europe, addressing viticulture, forestry, livestock transport, olive farming, and sustainable agriculture, respectively.

Rural communities often face challenges in selecting the most suitable connectivity technologies, as the options can be complex and unclear. The Decision-Making Support Tool (DST) addresses this issue by using LLMs to provide tailored recommendations. It helps end-users make informed decisions by analyzing their specific needs through a curated knowledge base and the Intelligent Connectivity Platform (ICP). The ICP enhances the DST by offering ranked connectivity solutions, integrating insights from various connectivity platforms within the project. COMMECT’s focus on empowering end-users with decision-making capabilities addresses both technological and socio-economic factors. The project highlights the importance of integrating terrestrial and non-terrestrial network solutions to provide comprehensive connectivity, demonstrating a commitment to enhancing connectivity in diverse and challenging rural environments. The DST, although in its initial stages, represents a strategic approach to leveraging AI and LLM technologies to facilitate decision-making. These models show promise in processing large datasets and generating insights, though their full potential requires further validation through field trials in the Living Labs. The next steps will focus on validating connectivity solutions through structured experimentation across the five LLMs. A key focus moving forward is ensuring that the KPIs (including network availability, energy consumption, and device connectivity) are fully aligned with the project’s defined goals.

In summary, COMMECT’s innovative integration of advanced connectivity technologies and decision support systems aims to bridge the digital divide, promoting sustainable development and competitiveness in rural areas. Future project phases will continue to validate and refine these solutions, ensuring they effectively meet the needs of

rural communities and contribute to broader socio-economic and environmental goals.

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